

Exploring English language teachers' perception of teaching the critical reading skills at college level, Hyderabad, Pakistan

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Abstract: This study attempts to investigate the perceptions of English Language Teachers about teaching the critical reading skills. Critical reading is considered one of the essential skills for students in today's world. One of the main objectives of teaching English subject at college level, Hyderabad, is also to promote critical reading skills. Therefore, this study sought to explore the perceptions of ELT teachers have about critical reading and also tried to investigate their understanding level about teaching critical reading skills. Qualitative research method was adopted to conduct this inquiry in which the techniques of classroom ethnography were used as research design. Data was collected into two phases. In first phase, the semi-structured interviews were taken from the twelve (12) English language Teachers who were teaching English at public colleges of Hyderabad, Pakistan. In second phase, classes of five (05) English language teachers were observed. Findings of this study reveals that most teachers had unclear about critical reading which indicates that they were not able to properly implement critical reading skills in their language classrooms. Result of this study suggests that reforms should be made at pre-service teachers training programs about teaching the critical reading skills so that ELT teachers can develop better understanding of this notion.

Keywords: critical thinking, critical reading, English language teaching and learning

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Introduction

Reading is considered the backbone of acquiring proficiency and accuracy in any language. It is the most basic and yet most essential skills for achieving success in different domains of the personal and professional life. It is a very important skill for students to fulfill different academic tasks. Fadlallah (2016) believes that "all our knowledge is increased

through reading” (p. 2). Reading is often seen as a process of gaining information but it is not as straight as seen. Languages are interlinked with socioeconomic powers. Languages generate the knowledge and knowledge in results generates the social structures. Knowledge is always socially established (McLaren, 2003). When languages establish the knowledge and political status quo then how the literacy generated as a result of reading can be considered apolitical or agenda-free. After the rise of critical approaches, reading is seen as a social activity that considerably affects the young mind to accept the dominating notions. Several frameworks and theories attempt to understand the reading processes through cognitive, cultural, and social perspectives. One of the most interesting guiding frameworks comes under the critical theory. It sees reading as an active process where the reader communicates with the text and tries to go beyond the surface level of meaning. Reading is now a social activity where the role of reader is changed from passive consumer of knowledge to the active judge of the text. Critical readers are not only supposed to read the text but are also expected to carefully evaluate every written detail. And later they are also expected to present their own views on the text. Critical thinking is a part of critical reading because this process of reading involves higher-order thinking skills like judging, making inferences, contrasting, comparing, analyzing, reasoning, and evaluating the text and also decoding the implicit meaning (Alvermann, Unrauand & Ruddell, 2013).

Critical reading is important for students to become critical thinker. In this age of information where production and reproduction of information and misinformation is done within seconds of clicks, it is important for students to critically analyze the arguments and deduce out the most rational conclusions so that they cannot come under influence of any dogmatic knowledge. Apart from this, research has also proven that critical reading help students to gain proficiency in languages. It is now with the fact that the teaching of critical reading has been made as an inevitable part of many language courses.

Research has shown that despite having huge importance of critical reading, English language teachers still teach reading skills with help of old traditional methods. They do not involve students into critical reading but just make them to comprehend the text. Teachers are often not very well aware of the impact which languages bring with them and even if some of them do they still fail to apply appropriate teaching methods in ETL classrooms. The existing pedagogies practiced by teachers for training students to read are insufficient to make students critical about things which they read. Most students can comprehend the text but are not trained to judge or evaluate it (Demirel & Sahinel, 1999, p. 25). Therefore, this present study sought to investigate the perceptions of English language teachers have about teaching the critical reading skills. It will try to explore that how far English teachers are aware of critical reading in terms of its concept, promotion, assessment and application. And it will also try to explore that how far teachers are aware of teachings methods and strategies require for teaching the critical reading skills.

1. To explore the perceptions of English teachers towards teaching of critical reading skills at college level.
2. To explore the extent to which English language teachers are aware of teaching the critical reading at the college level.

Literature Review

Several studies have been conducted in field of critical pedagogy dealing with subject of critical reading. All of these studies show the importance of critical reading have for students to gain critical consciousness and succeed in contemporary world. The investigation of Huges (2014) founded out that critical reading can play an important role in improving critical thinking of language learners. Critical reading involves readers into complex mental processes like analysis, logical reasoning, making comparisons, contrasting details, and evaluating the credibility of arguments etc. These activities help reader to reach to the logical conclusion and take better informed decisions. In this way critical reading help people to become critical thinker. The theoretical study conducted by AbdulMohsen S.Aloqaili (2011) also explored the well established connection between critical reading and critical thinking. This study utilizes schema

theory to show the relationship between reading and thinking. It concluded that reading improves the perceptions of readers; it gives reader more clearer account of the world and its affairs which later makes them to look at thing with critical angels.

Hamed, Behrouz, and Reza (2013) carried out research on two groups of students which were taught reading through two different methods. One group was taught reading through old traditional methods while other group was involved into critical reading. Findings of this study suggested that the first group students developed less interest in reading and they performed less in the post reading task. Students of second group were noticeably more active and shown great interest in reading and also performed far better than the first group in post reading tasks. This shows that how critical reading helps students to improve their performances. The efficacy of teaching reading skills through critical approaches was investigated by S.W.Yulianto (2015). For this study 59 young teachers were selected who were taught critical reading into eight different meetings. In all these sessions they were exposed to material containing real life issues. They were asked to analyze, discuss and evaluate the material which was presented to them. At the end of this short training program it was founded out that their proficiency of language has considerably improved. They developed keen interest in learning and reading more about ongoing issues and were willing to participate in class. It also make them autonomous learner who took charge of their own reading and tried to bring their own logical conclusions or understanding of the texts. Thus, considering the growing demands it has now become imperative for all ELT teachers and students to get to know about critical reading so that they can compete the world and be successful in their relevant fields.

Research also shows that despite having great importance of critical reading the English language teachers are still not well aware of the concept and teaching of critical reading. Most of ELT teachers affirms the importance of critical reading and supports the teaching of it in language classrooms but they themselves are unaware of its basic concept, promotion and assessment in real language classroom settings. Afanasjeva & Fedotova (2020) had done a survey on 15 teachers' participants to analyze their understanding about critical reading. The findings of this survey reveal that there is huge gap between what teachers' actually conceptualize and what they produce in classroom. 52.5% students participants in this research revealed that they learnt very little in critical reading classrooms and they usually find teachers confuse and less confident about the teaching of critical reading. And on other hand most teachers accepted the fact that they are not well trained about critical reading so they find it extremely difficult to teach students this skill. Similar study was carried out by Rui Yaun and Paul Stapleton (2019) but it was on the conception of critical thinking and the participants were the pre-service teachers. This study also concluded that teachers were not giving proper instructions about critical thinking or critical pedagogy so they showed very limited understanding about these concepts. It was recommended in this investigation that training programs should introduce proper sessions for critical pedagogy so that ELT teachers' can improve their cognizance about critical thinking and can easily implement it in their language classrooms. Matias A. Marin & Luisa de la Pave (2017) also concluded similar results where teachers were not fully aware of critical thinking or its applications. This study also suggested that education policies, EFL/ESL curriculum, language learning objectives and planning should be designed in a way so that teachers can get clear idea about teaching of critical pedagogy and they should also be told that how these things can be implemented successfully in language classrooms. These reforms can bring significant change in second language learning classrooms and can make students up to level of the advanced world. This study also revealed that critical thinking and reading are well explained and taught in other disciplines but English language curriculum still need to work on it.

Research Methodology

Qualitative method of inquiry is utilized to carry out this investigation. This method is considered suitable for a type of research which involves in-depth analysis of opinions, understanding and perceptions of people. According to Creswell (2013) qualitative research is a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a

social or human problem. And classroom ethnography is used as a research design. This design applies the ethnographic methods to understand the behaviours, interactions, practices, and activities happen within the formal setting of the classroom. Bloome and Green (2012) provides very rich data by involving range of tools from interviews, observations, audio – video recording and also help researcher to spend a very good amount of time on site of research and among the subjects. Classroom ethnography remained the most appropriate approach for this inquiry as it allowed the researcher to investigate the behaviour of participant in their natural settings.

Research participants & Sampling

Twelve English language teachers were selected from four public colleges of Hyderabad. All research participants had more than five (05) years of experience in teaching and during time of research they were teaching to students of grade XI-XII. All the participants were selected through convenience sampling.

Research Context

This research has been conducted on four public colleges of Hyderabad where English is taught as compulsory subject. All these colleges come under the department of Education, Sindh. The policy of National Curriculum 2006 has been implemented in all of these four colleges in which 'promoting critical thinking through reading' is one of the main objectives of teaching the English subject at XI-XII level.

Data Collection Tool

The data is collected into two phases. In First phase semi-structured interviews were taken from all the twelve English research participants. Semi-structured interviews can be employed when more useful information need to be obtained from focused and yet conversational two way communication with the participants (Anil Phatak, 2012). In second phase the classes of three teachers were observed to match the data of interview with their actual practices. Observation can offer a more "comprehensive and dynamic" appreciation of situations that cannot be as easily captured through other methods. (Liu & Maitlis 2010). Five classes of three teachers were observed; it means total 15 sessions were made the part of process. All these sessions were specifically dealing with the teaching of reading skills.

Data Analysis:

The analysis of data is done through the help of thematic model suggested by Braun and Clark (2006). It involved six steps, i.e. familiarization, generating initial codes, searching the themes, reviewing the themes, defining and naming the themes and producing the report.

Findings and Discussions

Interviews helped researcher in exploring the first research question which is about the understanding level of teachers about critical reading that how far they are clear about the idea of critical reading in terms of its conception and promotion. Following are the major findings of the data,

1- Supports the teaching of critical reading

All the research participants supported the teaching of critical reading at college level. They showed positive attitude towards promoting critical reading in English language classrooms. Some research participants thought it is important for students' confidence and performance in second language learning while other thought it bring creativity and innovation among students and make them informed citizens of the society who can take better decisions. Five Teachers (research participants) believed that the task of reading is not just the understanding of text but also to judge the quality of arguments. These teachers also believed that critical reading is also helpful in enhancing the thinking level of students. These responses show the positive beliefs of teachers towards critical reading which can resultantly impact their teaching choices to teach students reading through critical approaches. The quality and effectiveness of teaching are directly associated with the pedagogical choices and these choices are impacted by the beliefs and perceptions which teachers hold (Whittle, R & Amanda, 2018).

2- Lack of understanding of basic idea of critical reading

Although every participant in study supported the teaching of critical reading at college level but only four (04) out of twelve (12) participants showed the confidence that they clearly know about critical reading. Their responses were accurate for instance quoting here the response of one participant who knew what critical reading is: Participant 07 "I think critical reading is a type of reading where we evaluate a text. For instance, where the text is coming from? Who is the writer? Relating context to the text and presenting our own views on the text". Rest all other participants told the vague idea about critical reading and most of them have associated it with 'active reading' they were unable to distinguish between critical reading and active reading.

This response shows that the serious reforms needed to be taken to improve the understanding level of teachers about critical pedagogy in general and critical reading in particular because critically aware teachers can only make critical students. When teachers are themselves not aware of one notion then how are they going to implement that in their classes.

3- Lack of knowledge of teaching methods required for teaching the critical reading

Only five (05) research participants talked about dialogue, questioning and group discussions and rest all other mentioned the traditional strategies for teaching the reading skills. These five (05) participants also explicitly shared their experiences that how they made their students to challenge the text. Participant 05: "there was a disturbing passage about mannerism in which sitting on floor and wearing dhoti (Indian traditional piece of clothing) was shown in a bad light. I first asked my students to read and explain the passage then also asked their views on good manners which were presented in the text. When no one challenged the arguments then I posed them questions that how sitting on floor is bad while sitting on chair is not? That's how I led my students to challenge the text". Rest all other participants talked the about the traditional methods of teaching like comprehension, translation of difficult chunks, summarization etc.

These responses show that some teachers know the application of critical reading but still it was not sufficient to teach that level. Majority of teachers were still stuck to old methods which can only make students to read the text but not to judge or evaluate it. So proper training should be given to teachers so that they can know that how they can teach critical reading skills to their students successfully.

4- Focus on teaching of lower-order thinking skills

One of the main purposes of critical reading is to develop the higher order thinking skills of students but majority of responses depicts that the attention of teachers during reading classes is mainly on gaining factual information. like the strategies which most of them discussed like reading comprehension, guessing the meaning of difficult word through context, summarization of the central idea, searching the answers of the questions, telling the message of text etc. All these strategies can only involve students in finding the factual information of text. It cannot help students to gain good critical sight towards the text and hence can never be sufficient to make them critical thinker.

5- Challenges and concerns discussed by the teachers

During interview almost all participants also mentioned the concerns and challenges which act as hurdle and stop them to implement critical reading in classroom. First, they claimed that they get very less time to cover the syllabus. Seven (07) research participants said that the syllabus is too lengthy that they can only explain students the meaning of text and cannot involve them in any sort of analysis. Secondly they said that exams do not contain any question for testing the critical thinking of students. Teachers believed that exams are the big motivation for the students and when one thing is not the made part of exam then it is extremely challenging for them to motivate students to learn about that thing which is not the part of exams. Thirdly the low competence level of students; most of students are unable to grab the basic concept so it is difficult to teach critical reading skills to such students. Lastly curriculum also does not contain clear guidance of teaching the critical reading skills. Objectives do have the element of teaching critical thinking through reading but overall there is not any other clear instruction present that how critical reading can be implemented or assessed at college level. So these challenges make English language teachers to remain stuck to old teaching methods.

Observation helped researcher in investigating that how clearly and successfully teachers are able to teach critical reading skills to students. Following are the major findings from observation.

1- Focus on language development

It was observed that majority of reading sessions were focusing on development of linguistics skills of students. Fourteen (14) out of fifteen (15) sessions on reading classes involved activities related to vocabulary building. For instance, guessing the meaning of words through context, sentence making exercises, telling meaning of difficult words prior to lesson, giving home tasks of finding the meaning of words from dictionary and asking students to memorize all the newly learnt words. Nine (09) sessions were dedicated to teaching of grammar. For instance, identifying the tenses of the sentences, identifying words categories, looking for verb agreement in a sentences, etc. It can be said that primary objective of teachers remain to teach linguistics skills to students through help of reading tasks.

2- Focus on the Development of conceptual and critical thinking

It was observed that most sessions involved the usage of lower-order thinking exercises. Only Five (05) out of fifteen (15) sessions of the total observed classes, teachers actually tried to elevate the level of students by involving them in higher-order thinking tasks. Some major findings related to the development of critical thinking includes, posing questions: In three (03) sessions teachers posed text-related questions before starting the chapter and in the other two (02) sessions teachers asked the questions while explaining the content. For instance, while teaching the chapter "The Dam broke" teachers asked in the middle how would have student reacted if they saw anyone running anxiously towards certain direction. The teacher also gave them time to evaluate the situation before answering. In two (02) sessions teachers involved students in group tasks related to reading. In four (04) sessions teachers led students to relate the content to their real life. These sessions mainly remained dominant by teachers as students were unable to relate things to their personal experiences. Students' participation was seen very less during these sessions. Activities focusing related to analysis of content were not recorded. Overall activities which might have involved students in higher order thinking skills were not observed. It can be said that the focus of teacher remain on improving the lower order thinking skills of students.

3- Cultural Dimension

In two (02) reading sessions teachers asked students to compare the culture presented in one lesson with their own culture to find the similarities and dissimilarities. Discussion related to that how some values or practices are sidelined was not observed. A very little part of three (03) sessions dealt with the concept of inclusivity. For instance, during chapter "respecting self and others" teacher involved students in discussion that how every culture and every human being is equally important and respected.

The data clearly shows that English language teachers are not well trained about teaching the critical reading skills to college level students. Therefore, training programs should be introduced for ELT teachers which can make them familiar with teaching methods of critical reading skills and also train them that how they can teach this skill effectively and efficiently. Moreover, more exercises and content related to critical reading should be introduced in the syllabus of English language so that teachers and students both feel motivated towards learning of this important skill. And clear decisions should be made in terms of curriculum development and exams pattern so that instructional guidelines should be aligned with exam pattern and good space should be given to teaching of critical reading at college level. And lastly exams should carry questions related to testing of critical reading skills of students so that students should be easily encouraged to study about critical reading.

Conclusion

Research reveals that critical thinking is very important for students to succeed in contemporary world. And critical reading plays inevitable role in enhancing the critical thinking skills of students. Thus, it suggests implementing critical reading strategies in English language classrooms so that students can meet criteria of today's world. The results of this

study clearly show that how challenging it is to teach critical reading skills therefore teachers should be well trained so that they can fulfill this task more efficiently and diligently

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